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Role of Postbiotics Functional Metabolites of *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae* on Productive Performance in Cattle and Buffalo

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Abstract

the present study demonstrated the application of microbial base postbiotics as functional metabolites on the productivity of cattle and buffalo. Two separate groups of cows (n=120) and buffaloes (n=45) were segregated as G1-control (Plain feed CP-22%) and G2-treated (Plain feed CP-22% + microbial metabolites) under trial on the same farm. Switchover trial strategy was adopted for the real time results with the gap of 15 days of treatment.

The buffaloes in G1 had average milk yield of 8.29L, while supplementation of 15g of postbiotics in G2 group increased milk production to an average of 9.23L. A slightly significant results were obtained in SNF and milk fat. An elevation in SNF value of 0.02% in G2 group of buffalo was recorded. Milk fat in G1 group of buffalo was 5.52% while uplift in G2 was recorded with 5.55%. In cow trial, highly significant results were obtained in G2 with an average of 10.1L milk yield, in comparison to G1, had an average of 8.49L milk yield and 0.71% of SNF in G2 group of cows was recorded. G1 of cows, recorded 4.71% of milk fat while in G2 8.51% of milk fat was observed. In cows, an elevated total volatile fatty acids up to 10.4mM was recorded in G2 compared to G1 with 51.4mM volatile fatty acids

Keywords: Animal health, milk yield, microbial metabolites, postbiotics

INTRODUCTION

Animal health, better productive performance and feed utilization along with animal food safety have always been the prime concerns for cattle. Microbial research has played its role by facilitating the animal with desired fermentation, removing pathogens and decreasing the occurrence of ruminal disorders. Digestive tract resides

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millions of microbes inside the intestinal tissues through opportunistic invasion (Cristofori et al., 2021). Commensal microbes play an active role in nutrient supply (Cammack et al., 2018). In case of ruminants, these microbes provide the animal with energy by releasing the end products of microbial fermentation in the stomach (Newbold & Ramos-Morales, 2020). These end products help the animal in better immunity (Wang et al., 2025). Hence proving that animal health is closely related with this microbial ecology inside the gastrointestinal tract (Vargas-Bello-Pérez et al., 2024).

In recent time, a proposal with term 'Postbiotics' suggested that viability of bacterial microbe is not a necessity for better gut health of an organism (Aguilar-Toalá et al., 2018). This idea gave a new dimension to the research that lead to the preparation of inanimate microorganisms (Salminen et al., 2021). The studies on non-viable microbes got the edge by providing the animal with safety advantages as well as lower possibilities of infection or any kind of inflammatory response and microbial translocation (Tang & Lu, 2019). Postbiotic components may include inactivated microbial cell or its cell wall, peptides, vitamins, bacteriocin, proteins and bioactive metabolites (Aguilar-Toalá et al., 2018). The preparation of postbiotic components depends on the strain used, substrate availability and its growth conditions (Teame et al., 2020). Keeping consumers demand of eliminating synthetic therapeutic compounds in mind and following the strict regulatory measures, the metabolites released from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* can be a good substitute to tackle antibiotic resistance (Burdick Sanchez et al., 2021).

Since various research studies supported the use of yeast strain in the cattle feed by optimizing the feed intake (Pang et al., 2022). It resulted in an increased milk production along with visible weight gain (Amin & Mao, 2021), giving a new dimension in the field of veterinary. Metabolites released from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* under favorable conditions and the nutrients availability (in vitro conditions) can propose to be beneficial postbiotic product. This study evaluated the impact of extra pure metabolites (released from yeast – *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* under in vitro conditions) on ruminal health of cattle and its role in animal health and productivity.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

The functional microbial metabolites extracted from *Sacchromyces cerevisiae* were procured in the form of light grey color powder as extra pure metabolites (XPM). Trial was conducted on two groups of cattle selected randomly at an established dairy farm. Both groups (G1 and G2) of cows (n=120) and buffalo (n=45) were separately under study, with a trial period of thirty days. The research study was conducted according to the Institutional Biosafety Committee keeping in view the Bioethical and Environmental Safety Perspectives.

Switchover trial strategy was opted for animals i.e. control group becomes the experimental group and vice versa after fifteen days. The experimental group was supplemented with 15g of postbiotics functional metabolites. Total duration of trial was divided into three periods: (a) Adaptation period (b) period 1 and (c) period 2.

(a)Adaptation period counted for four days before trial, (b) Period 1 consisted of G1–control group i.e. cattle receiving plain feed CP-22% and G2-experimental group i.e. cattle fed with plain feed CP-22% + microbial metabolites. (c) Period 2 included switching of groups within the trial period after 15 days, G1 being experimental group fed with CP-22% + microbial metabolites and G2 switched towards control group with a feed regime including CP-22% only. In adaptation period all the data was collected of both groups prior to the start of trial. Both groups were screened for Surf Field Mastitis test (SFMT) (Karabasanavar et al., 2021) before trial (all negative) and every fifth day of trial (Table 1).

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Table 1. Distribution of animals for feed supplement trial

Periods	Trial days	Animal groups	Feeding regime
Adaptation phase	04	G1 (no treatment)	Plain Feed
		G2 (no treatment)	
I	15	G1 (control)	G1 (Plain feed)
		G2 (Experimental)	G2 (Plain feed + 15g postbiotics functional metabolites)
II	15	G1(Experimental)	G1 (Plain feed + 15g postbiotics functional metabolites)
		G2(Control)	G2 (Plain feed)

The study evaluated the impact of extra pure metabolites on milk production of the experimental group. Milk samples were collected on every fifth day of the trial to analyze the milk composites like solids not Fat (SNF), volatile fatty acids (AOAC Method 996.06) and milk fat (Feldsine et al., 2002). High performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) was performed to evaluate volatile fatty acid production in animal rumen (Fernández et al., 2016).

RESULTS

Productive performance in Cow and Buffalo

The animals under trial with metabolites in diet (G2) reported better productive performance with an increase of 0.92-1.6L milk yield. During trial period, the G1 buffaloes showed an average milk production of 8.29L. However, it was observed that G2 had an average milk yield of 9.23L supporting its role in enhancing the animal productivity and daily performance of the buffalo. In the same way, when trial on cow group was conducted, the G2 group fed with microbial metabolites totally favored the results in metabolites, by showing great positive impact on the productive performance of the trial animals. Improved yield performance was reported in the G2 with an average of 10.1L as shown in the figure1.1, while the control group G1 showed an average of 8.49L of milk yield.

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Fig 1 Impact of postbiotics functional metabolites on milk yield in control vs postbiotics treated group is presented with mean \pm SD

The findings of buffalo trial also revealed the influence of metabolites on milk quality, as the buffalo group (G2) fed with metabolites showed increased SNF value up to 9.22% in comparison to control group with 8.51% SNF value during trial period. The milk fat content in the treated group G2 had a mean value of 5.55% while G1 reported decreased milk fat percentage of 5.52% as shown in the figure 1.2. In cow trial, the better values of SNF and milk fats supported the positive impact of metabolites on milk quality, as the study concluded the SNF percentage of G2 to be 8.59% and mean milk fats i.e. 4.81%. On comparison with G1, that showed SNF value of 8.57% and milk fats 4.77%.

Fig 2 Results of milk quality parameters supplemented with postbiotics functional metabolites

Impact on Volatile Fatty Acid Production

The mean composition of the mixture of volatile fatty acids in the rumen liquor during the feeding period of animal diet showed variation, with clear improved values of 10.4mM in the G2 of the trial. In case of acetate, an

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individual increase was observed with the figure of 28mM while the G1 group showed the acetate concentration of 22mM during trial. Values of propionate also reported to strike the figure of 28.4mM in group G2. On the other hand, the G1 reported 24.8mM propionate concentration.

Fig 3 Competitive evaluation of VFA in control vs postbiotics treated group

DISCUSSION

The addition of fungal supplement in animal feed has shown great potential in dairy industry (Arambel et al., 1987; Hussein et al., 2024). In a review (Pang et al., 2022) addition of yeast in ruminant's feed, improved the milk quality. In the same way, studies having yeast supplementation has shown positive impact on animal's Dry Matter Intake along with milk production (Zhang et al., 2024). In current study, post-biotic metabolites prepared, are made readily available for the animal gut resulting in an obvious influence on milk yield. In another study, data collected from trial with feed additives of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* showed improved productivity, digestibility and dry matter intake (Mohammed et al., 2018). In the recent past, a study on Mongolian ram lambs was conducted, for the impact of yeast culture in diet also reported, a promote in productivity and weight gain (Chen et al., 2024). Many studies in the recent past reported the influence of yeast culture on cattle's milk composites (Chae et al., 2024). A study by Jiang (Jiang et al., 2024) stated the role of microbial metabolites in improving the composition of milk in dairy buffaloes. As in a study, Nocek also reported the increase in animal milk protein and milk fats, this increase may also be justified with the explanation of yeast's role in rumen fermentation and better nutrient digestibility, this led to enhancement in the ammonia uptake and more microbial protein production (Nocek et al., 2003). An increase in the microbial load of rumen by this effective digestion could also influence the milk fat content (Zhang et al., 2022). Vazirigozar in the research study reported lowered milk fat when given microbial and enzyme supplement in their feed (Vazirigozar et al., 2018) An increase in milk fat in dairy cows reviewed by Amin (Amin & Mao, 2021) also favors the results of current study.

In the present study an increase in the Volatile Fatty Acid in the rumen liquor was observed which is consistent to one of the previous studies that reported the effect of yeast in rumen with an increased molar proportion of acetate and acetate: propionate ratio. Similarly, an elevation in concentration of butyrate was observed by the use yeast supplementation in dairy cow (Zhu et al., 2017). On contrary, a study with addition of chromium yeast in mid-lactation dairy cows revealed no impact on ruminal pH and total volatile fatty acid (Shan et al., 2024). A

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study conducted on finishing bulls, reported a potential contribution on rumen VFA profile especially in propionate suggesting the contribution of active dry yeast in modulation of composition of rumen bacterial communities (Feng et al., 2024).

CONCLUSION

From this trial study, it may be concluded that the metabolites of yeast can be a great feed supplement with readily available minerals, vitamins and a biofortification source for malnourished and underfed population. This study supports the marked influence of feed supplement on milk quality and quantity; it also contributes a substantial effect on the rumen microbes.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

DMI Dry Matter Intake

HPLC High performance Liquid Chromatography

SFMT Surf Field Mastitis test

SNF solid not Fat

VFA Volatile Fatty Acid

WHO World Health Organization

REFERENCE

- Aguilar-Toalá, J., Garcia-Varela, R., Garcia, H., Mata-Haro, V., González-Córdova, A., Vallejo-Cordoba, B., & Hernández-Mendoza, A. (2018). Postbiotics: An evolving term within the functional foods field. *Trends in food science & technology*, 75, 105-114.
- Amin, A. B., & Mao, S. (2021). Influence of yeast on rumen fermentation, growth performance and quality of products in ruminants: A review. *Animal nutrition*, 7(1), 31-41.
- Arambel, M., Wiedmeier, R., & Walters, J. (1987). Influence of donor animal adaptation to added yeast culture and/or *Aspergillus oryzae* fermentation extract on in vitro rumen fermentation.
- Burdick Sanchez, N. C., Broadway, P. R., & Carroll, J. A. (2021). Influence of yeast products on modulating metabolism and immunity in cattle and swine. *Animals*, 11(2), 371.
- Cammack, K. M., Austin, K. J., Lamberson, W. R., Conant, G. C., & Cunningham, H. C. (2018). RUMINNAT NUTRITION SYMPOSIUM: Tiny but mighty: the role of the rumen microbes in livestock production. *Journal of animal science*, 96(2), 752-770.
- Chae, J.-B., Schoofs, A. D., & McGill, J. L. (2024). Beneficial effects of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* fermentation postbiotic products on calf and cow health and plausible mechanisms of action. *Frontiers in Animal Science*, 5, 1491970.
- Chen, H., Liu, S., Li, S., Li, D., Li, X., Xu, Z., & Liu, D. (2024). Effects of yeast culture on growth performance, immune function, antioxidant capacity and hormonal profile in Mongolian ram lambs. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 11, 1424073.
- Cristofori, F., Dargenio, V. N., Dargenio, C., Miniello, V. L., Barone, M., & Francavilla, R. (2021). Anti-inflammatory and immunomodulatory effects of probiotics in gut inflammation: a door to the body. *Frontiers in immunology*, 12, 578386.

- Feldsine, P., Abeyta, C., & Andrews, W. H. (2002). AOAC International methods committee guidelines for validation of qualitative and quantitative food microbiological official methods of analysis. *Journal of AOAC international*, 85(5), 1187-1200.
- Feng, X., Luan, J., Yang, D., Jin, Y., & Geng, C. (2024). Active Dry Yeast (*Saccharomyces Cerevisiae*) Improves Rumen Fatty Acid Profile by Regulating Rumen Bacteria in Finishing Bulls. *Journal of Animal Science and Technology*.
- Fernández, R., Dinsdale, R. M., Guwy, A. J., & Premier, G. C. (2016). Critical analysis of methods for the measurement of volatile fatty acids. *Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology*, 46(3), 209-234.
- Hussein, W., Ramadan, W. A., Mahmoud, F. E., & Fahim, S. (2024). The Impact of Rhizosphere Bacterial Strains as Biofertilizers: Inhibiting Fungal Growth and Enhancing the Growth and Immunity of Sprouted Barley as an Alternative Livestock Feed. *Jordan Journal of Biological Sciences*, 17(4).
- Jiang, B., Qin, C., Xu, Y., Song, X., Fu, Y., Li, R., Liu, Q., & Shi, D. (2024). Multi-omics reveals the mechanism of rumen microbiome and its metabolome together with host metabolome participating in the regulation of milk production traits in dairy buffaloes. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 15, 1301292.
- Karabasanavar, N., Manjunatha, L., Jeevan, M., & Naveenkumar, G. (2021). Evaluation of Surf Field Mastitis Test (SFMT) For the Detection of Subclinical Mastitis in Dairy Cows. *Asian Journal of Dairy and Food Research*, 40(4), 380-383.
- Mohammed, S. F., Mahmood, F. A., & Abas, E. R. (2018). A review on effects of yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) as feed additives in ruminants performance. *J. Entomol. Zool. Stud*, 6(2), 629-635.
- Newbold, C., & Ramos-Morales, E. (2020). Ruminant microbiome and microbial metabolome: effects of diet and ruminant host. *Animal*, 14(S1), s78-s86.
- Nocek, J., Kautz, W., Leedle, J., & Block, E. (2003). Direct-fed microbial supplementation on the performance of dairy cattle during the transition period. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 86(1), 331-335.
- Pang, Y., Zhang, H., Wen, H., Wan, H., Wu, H., Chen, Y., Li, S., Zhang, L., Sun, X., & Li, B. (2022). Yeast probiotic and yeast products in enhancing livestock feeds utilization and performance: An overview. *Journal of Fungi*, 8(11), 1191.
- Salminen, S., Collado, M. C., Endo, A., Hill, C., Lebeer, S., Quigley, E. M., Sanders, M. E., Shamir, R., Swann, J. R., & Szajewska, H. (2021). The International Scientific Association of Probiotics and Prebiotics (ISAPP) consensus statement on the definition and scope of postbiotics. *Nature reviews Gastroenterology & hepatology*, 18(9), 649-667.
- Shan, Q., Ma, F., Huang, Q., Wo, Y., & Sun, P. (2024). Chromium yeast promotes milk protein synthesis by regulating ruminal microbiota and amino acid metabolites in heat-stressed dairy cows. *Animal nutrition*.
- Tang, C., & Lu, Z. (2019). Health promoting activities of probiotics. *Journal of Food Biochemistry*, 43(8), e12944.
- Teame, T., Wang, A., Xie, M., Zhang, Z., Yang, Y., Ding, Q., Gao, C., Olsen, R. E., Ran, C., & Zhou, Z. (2020). Paraprobiotics and postbiotics of probiotic Lactobacilli, their positive effects on the host and action mechanisms: A review. *Frontiers in nutrition*, 7, 570344.
- Vargas-Bello-Pérez, E., Altermann, E., Tudisco, R., Zhang, Q., Puniya, A. K., & Cherdthong, A. (2024). Recent advances and perspectives on the gastrointestinal microbiota of small ruminants. *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 15, 1473958.
- Vazirigohar, M., Dehghan-Banadaky, M., Rezayazdi, K., Nejati-Javaremi, A., Mirzaei-Alamouti, H., & Patra, A. (2018). Effects of diets containing supplemental fats on ruminal fermentation and milk odd-and branched-chain fatty acids in dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, 101(7), 6133-6141.
- Wang, S., Li, E., Luo, Z., Li, X., Liu, Z., Li, W., Wang, X., Qin, J. G., & Chen, L. (2025). Dietary yeast culture can protect against chronic heat stress by improving the survival, antioxidant capacity, immune response, and gut health of juvenile Chinese mitten crab (*Eriocheir sinensis*). *Aquaculture*, 596, 741910.

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- Zhang, H., Elolimy, A. A., Akbar, H., Thanh, L. P., Yang, Z., & Looor, J. J. (2022). Association of residual feed intake with peripartal ruminal microbiome and milk fatty acid composition during early lactation in Holstein dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science*, *105*(6), 4971-4986.
- Zhang, Q., Ma, L., Zhang, X., Jia, H., Guo, Y., Zhang, J., & Wang, J. (2024). Feeding live yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) improved performance of mid-lactation dairy cows by altering ruminal bacterial communities and functions of serum antioxidation and immune responses. *BMC Veterinary Research*, *20*(1), 1-12.
- Zhu, W., Wei, Z., Xu, N., Yang, F., Yoon, I., Chung, Y., Liu, J., & Wang, J. (2017). Effects of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* fermentation products on performance and rumen fermentation and microbiota in dairy cows fed a diet containing low quality forage. *Journal of Animal Science and Biotechnology*, *8*, 1-9.